

MÜSƏLMAN DÜNYASINDA GEDƏN INTEQRASIYA PROSESLƏRİ

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s.e.f.d.

BDU-nun Diplomatiya və müasir inteqrasiya prosesləri kafedrası

Xülasə. Müsəlman dünyası, ümumi dini, tarixi və mədəni köklərə malik olmasına baxmayaraq, inteqrasiya istiqamətində qarşısında ciddi maneələr dayanır. Bir tərəfdən, müsəlman ölkələrinin birliyə ehtiyacı regiondakı sabitlik, iqtisadi inkişaf və siyasi müstəqillik üçün həyati əhəmiyyət kəsb edir. Digər tərəfdən, məzhəb ixtilafları, siyasi rəqabətlər və geosiyasi maraqlar inteqrasiya səylərinə mane olur.

Bu məqalədə müsəlman dünyasında inteqrasiya cəhdlərinin tarixi və müasir formaları, qarşılaşılan problemlər və gələcək perspektivlər həmçinin müsəlman dünyasında baş verən inteqrasiya prosesləri siyasi, iqtisadi və mədəni aspektlərdə təhlil edilir. Tədqiqatın əsas məqsədi İslam Əməkdaşlıq Təşkilatı və digər regional platformalar çərçivəsində üzv dövlətlər arasında əməkdaşlıq meyillərini araşdırmaq, inteqrasiya səylərinin qarşısında duran əsas maneələri və imkanları müəyyənləşdirməkdir. Məqalədə müsəlman ölkələrinin qarşılıqlı münasibətləri, həmrəylik təşəbbüsləri, geosiyasi maraqlar və dini-mədəni birliyin rolu nəzərdən keçirilir. Nəticədə göstərilir ki, bəzi müsbət təşəbbüslərə baxmayaraq, siyasi ziddiyyətlər, iqtisadi asılılıqlar və ideoloji fərqliliklər inteqrasiyanı ləngidir. Araşdırma bu proseslərin gücləndirilməsi üçün daha sabit, inklüziv və qarşılıqlı maraqlara əsaslanan əməkdaşlıq mexanizmlərinin vacibliyini vurğulayır.

Açar sözlər: müsəlman dünyası, əməkdaşlıq, mədəni birlik, inteqrasiya, platformalar, qarşılıqlı maraq.

INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN THE MUSLIM WORLD

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Summary. Despite having common religious historical and cultural roots, the Muslim world faces serious obstacles to integration. On the one hand the need for unity among Muslim countries is vital for regional stability, economic development and political independence. On the other hand sectarian differences, political rivalries and geopolitical interests hinder integration efforts.

This article analyzes the historical and contemporary forms of integration efforts in the Muslim world, the problems encountered and future prospects, as well as the integration processes taking place in the Muslim world in political, economic and cultural aspects. The main objective of the study is to examine the trends in cooperation between member states within the framework of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation and other regional platforms and to identify the main obstacles and opportunities facing integration efforts. The article examines the mutual relations of Muslim countries, solidarity initiatives, geopolitical interests and the role of religious and cultural unity. As a result it is shown that despite some positive initiatives, political contradictions, economic dependencies and ideological differences slow down integration. The study highlights the importance of more stable, inclusive and mutually beneficial cooperation mechanisms to strengthen these processes.

Keywords: Muslim world, cooperation, cultural unity, integration, platforms, mutual interest.

Introduction

In the modern system of international relations, integration processes have become one of the main mechanisms of interstate cooperation. As in the case of the European Union, ASEAN and other regional associations, countries in different regions strive for closer cooperation on the basis of common interests, common culture, economic and political goals. This trend is also evident in the Muslim world. In the modern era of accelerating globalization, integration processes which form the basis of regional and religious-cultural unity, play an important role in the formation of international relations. In this context the integration efforts taking place in the Muslim world and the solidarity initiatives of Islamic countries located in different regions are of particular importance. However these integration initiatives in many cases fail to reach the desired level due to various political, economic and sectarian interests.

The article examines the essence, forms and main challenges of integration processes taking place among Muslim countries. The aim of the article is to analyze regional and international initiatives aimed at ensuring unity in the Islamic world, to compare successful and unsuccessful experiences. The approach to the topic is based on analytical and comparative analysis methods.

Relevance of the topic

The Muslim world is currently going through a period of geopolitical changes, ideological divisions and economic instability. In the context of the re-establishment of the global balance of power, the efforts of Islamic countries to unite and cooperate are of great importance in terms of both regional security and socio-economic development. The activation of institutions such as the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), the increase in joint defense and economic initiatives, and the attempts of Muslim states to unite on the basis of common values and interests further increase the relevance of integration processes in this direction. At the same time, the ongoing sectarian conflicts, geopolitical competition and foreign interventions in the Muslim world create serious obstacles to this integration. In such a context, it is an important issue from a scientific and practical point of view to study the real possibilities and difficulties of integration in the Islamic world and to identify effective models and mechanisms in this area

Purpose of the topic

The main purpose of this article is to analyze the integration processes existing in the Muslim world from political, economic and cultural aspects, to determine the successes and limitations of these processes. The study aims to study the cooperation initiatives taking place between Islamic countries at both regional and international levels, their institutional foundations (especially the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Gulf Cooperation Council, the Islamic Development Bank, etc.) and their real impact potential.

The geographical scope of the study covers the main regions where Muslim countries are located - the Middle East, Central Asia, North Africa, Southeast Asia and parts of the African continent that are part of the Islamic world. At the same time, the role of geopolitical actors (the USA, Russia, China, the European Union, etc.) influencing these integration efforts is also touched upon.

The study is mainly based on analytical and comparative analysis methods; different integration models and their levels of success are compared, cause-effect relationships are established and possible scenarios for the future are put forward.

Methodological approach

The study mainly used analytical and comparative analysis methods. The existing integration initiatives among Muslim countries were analyzed in political, economic and cultural areas, and different approaches were compared in different regions. Using a historical approach, the stages of formation of integration processes were traced, and institutional and functional analyses were also conducted.

The concept of integration in the Muslim world and historical stages

The concept of integration generally implies the unification of different states or political associations based on common interests through mutual cooperation, and the strengthening of relations through unified structures and institutions [4, p.154]. This concept is widely used in international

relations in the context of regional cooperation, economic blocs and political unions. In the Muslim world, the concept of integration includes both religious-cultural unity and political-economic solidarity [11, p.85]. The historical roots of integration attempts in the Islamic world date back to the early periods of Islam - the Caliphate period. Especially during the period of the Rashid Caliphs (632–661) and the Umayyad-Abbasid period, unity was observed in the Islamic world in political and administrative terms centralized governance covering vast territories was formed. During the Umayyad (661–750) and Abbasid (750–1258) periods, Muslims were united under a single political, religious and cultural system in vast territories. During these periods the Islamic world not only achieved internal integration but also became a global center of trade and science[15, p.202]. This period can be considered as the "classical stage of Islamic integration". Between the 14th and 19th centuries, the Ottoman Empire acted as a new unifying force in the Muslim world. The Ottoman sultans bearing the title of caliph, tried to play the role of political and religious leaders of the Islamic world. During this period, the centralized integration of Muslims continued to a certain extent. However in later periods, especially during the sectarian divisions that began with the Ottoman-Safavid rivalry and the period of European colonialism, the Islamic world began to fragment politically. In the 19th and 20th centuries, a number of ideological movements emerged in order to restore unity among Muslim peoples - pan-Islamism, the idea of a universal caliphate, and anti-colonial resistance movements. This period can be characterized as the "stage of ideological integration attempts". In the 19th century the idea of Pan-Islamism emerged in response to the imperialist pressures of the West. Pan-Islamism encouraged the unification of Muslims around the world and the struggle for common interests. Especially during the reign of the Ottoman Sultan Abdulhamid II this idea became an integral part of state policy. Modern integration efforts in the Muslim world began to take shape mainly after the second half of the 20th century. The changes in the system of international relations after World War II, the acceleration of the decolonization process and the emergence of new independent Muslim states made these integration efforts even more urgent. After World War II with the independence of Muslim countries, a new stage was entered. The establishment of the Organization of the Islamic Conference (now the Organization of Islamic Cooperation - OIC) in Morocco in 1969 is an important stage in this process. This period is now characterized as the "institutional integration stage". In the 21st century especially the events of September 11, the Arab Spring, civil wars in the Middle East and the global wave of Islamophobia have re-emerged the need for solidarity and joint action among Muslim countries. However at the same time, political competition, sectarian differences and external influences have slowed down integration efforts during this period. These historical stages show that the integration process in the Muslim world is cyclical - from time to time there are ups and downs but religious and cultural common ground continues to maintain the potential for integration.

Regional view: integration processes in the Middle East, Central Asia, North Africa and other regions

Since the Muslim world encompasses states located in different geographical regions, integration processes also differ according to the political, economic and social characteristics of these regions [10, p.117]. For this reason the level and nature of integration in each region has developed with different criteria.

Middle East. Although the Middle East region has rich energy resources, religious and cultural common values, these advantages have sometimes led to competition instead of stimulating integration. The struggle for influence between powers such as Saudi Arabia, Iran and Turkey in the region complicates integration.

Although the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) provides a partially functional example of cooperation in this region, disagreements between member states, especially the Qatar crisis (2017) have undermined the effectiveness of the organization. The civil wars in Syria and Yemen, and the unstable situation in Iraq are also factors preventing the formation of regional unity.

Central Asia. After the secession of the former USSR, the Muslim countries of Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan) began to build new models of statehood, which created both opportunities and challenges for regional integration.

The rapprochement of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan in recent years, as well as initiatives for cooperation in the customs and transport sectors between the Central Asian states, have created a positive dynamic. At the same time, these countries participate in joint projects within the framework of both the OIC and the Organization of Turkic States (OTS). However the geopolitical influence of Russia and China in the region is changing the nature of integration and limiting it to economic cooperation.

North Africa. Although the Arab-Muslim identity is strong in this region, which consists of countries such as Egypt, Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia, integration efforts are mainly realized within the pan-Arab framework [14, p.243]. Although certain initiatives have been put forward within the framework of the League of Arab States, effective results have not been achieved.

The preference of North African countries for closer economic relations with the European Union has kept regional Muslim integration in the background. However cooperation between these countries and Islamic countries continues within the framework of the OIC and the African Union.

Southeast Asia and other regions. In Indonesia, Malaysia, Brunei and other Southeast Asian countries, Islam is more a religious and cultural identity than a state system. Although these countries cooperate within regional organizations such as ASEAN, Islamic-based integration initiatives are weak.

Although Indonesia and Malaysia are active within the OIC, geographical distance and regional priorities limit the depth of this integration.

Islamic countries in Africa. Niger, Mali, Burkina Faso, Chad and other African countries with large Muslim populations are attempting to integrate in the areas of Islamic banking, humanitarian cooperation and education. However the activities of armed groups in this region, the weakness of states and institutional problems make integration difficult. Nevertheless, the humanitarian structures of the Islamic Development Bank and the OIC are operating in this region.

Against the background of all these regional differences, the relevance of integration initiatives based on common cultural, religious and historical values in the Muslim world is increasing. Global challenges, common problems such as Islamophobia, security threats and energy policy, necessitate greater rapprochement of Islamic countries [2, p.189]. In this regard, the topic requires serious scientific analysis at both the theoretical and practical levels. In this context, a deeper analysis of the integration potential of Muslim countries, a comparative study of examples of success and failure and the identification of effective models of cooperation at the regional and global levels have become necessary.

Institutional foundations and the role of organizations (OIC, GCC, etc.)

The organizations that play a key role in implementing integration efforts in the Muslim world, by their nature, cover political, economic and humanitarian fields. These organizations aim to promote unity among Islamic countries, strengthen cooperation and protect mutual interests. The most important organizations are the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), the Islamic Development Bank (IDB) and the Turkic States Organization (TSO).

The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) established in 1969 is the largest Islamic organization in the world, comprising 57 member states. The organization's goal is to promote political, economic and cultural cooperation among its member states. The OIC is also an important platform for making decisions aimed at protecting the common interests of the Islamic world [21, p.193]. The OIC is often called the UN of the Muslim world. Since its establishment, the OIC has been particularly active in the fields of humanitarian aid, education and social cooperation. To strengthen solidarity and cooperation among member states; To protect the rights and interests of Muslim peoples; To carry out joint activities in the political, economic, social and cultural fields.

For example, the OIC has created many sub-organizations and institutions that provide assistance to disaster-stricken countries, combat disease and implement development projects. The OIC's practical

impact is sometimes limited because of differences in political and strategic vision among member states. However the organization's influence on political issues is limited by the divergent interests of some member states.

Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC)

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) was established in 1981 by Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman and Qatar. This organization mainly aims to cooperate in the areas of economic integration and energy policies. The main role of the GCC is to expand trade relations between member states, create common markets and jointly manage energy resources. Within the framework of this organization: Joint economic projects (for example, the Gulf railway project), Joint security initiatives (for example, the idea of the "Joint Military Forces"), Attempts to create a free trade area have been made. However, the Qatar crisis (2017–2021) showed that political disagreements can seriously undermine such regional integration initiatives. The GCC's role in regional security issues has also increased, especially political stability and mutual security initiatives in the Gulf region are based on the activities of this organization. However, in recent years, political differences, such as the Qatar crisis have negatively affected the effectiveness of the GCC.

Islamic Development Bank (IDB)

It was established in 1975 and provides financial resources to support the economic development of its member states. The bank also finances the infrastructure and social projects of its member states by providing loans and investments for projects. This organization aims to strengthen the economies of Islamic countries ensure social and economic progress in underdeveloped regions. The role of the IDB is not limited to economic development. It is also active in areas such as strengthening trade relations, sharing advanced technologies and ensuring regional stability. The IDB implements many cooperation initiatives, especially in the areas of food security, education and health.

Organization of Turkic States

The Organization of Turkic States (OTS), formerly known as the Turkic Council, changed its name in 2009 to focus on broader regional cooperation. The OTS is primarily focused on increasing cooperation between countries belonging to the Turkic language family. The member states of this organization – Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan – provide mutual cooperation and support in various fields. The OTS's activities are particularly evident in education, trade, culture and security issues. The historical and cultural ties between the Turkic world allow this organization to be further strengthened. The OTS also implements a number of joint projects to promote regional stability and protect the strategic interests of its member states.

At the same time developments on the international stage – the Russia-Ukraine war, the West-East confrontation, and the growing economic ties between China and Central Asia – make the need for Turkic states to increase coordination among themselves even more urgent. The increased activity of leading Central Asian countries such as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan within the framework of the TBT is also an indication of the ongoing nature of this process.

The historical roots of integration among Turkic states are based on common ethnicity, linguistic unity, cultural values and ancient statehood traditions. Turkic peoples have established states, created trade routes and formed a common culture for millennia in a vast geography stretching from Central Asia to Anatolia. Great Turkic empires such as the Hun, Goyturk, Uyghur, Seljuk and Ottoman empires demonstrate that the joint political and cultural life of these peoples was historically possible and realistic (16). In particular, the Goyturk Khaganate (VI-VIII centuries) proved the possibility of unified political structures among Turkic peoples for the first time, and the system of governance based on the principle of "El (state) and Tora (law)" laid the foundation of Turkic political culture. The Orkhon-Yenisei monuments of this period are considered a clear example of linguistic and cultural unity among Turkic peoples. In subsequent periods through the Seljuk and Ottoman empires, Turkic-Muslim culture was enriched and a unified civilizational space was formed.

The independence of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan with the collapse of the USSR in 1991 marked the beginning of a new phase of integration in the Turkic world. Turkey played a central role in this process establishing diplomatic relations with the Turkic-speaking republics and implementing various projects in the fields of education and culture (9). Starting from the first summit held in Ankara in 1992, coordination efforts among the Turkic-speaking states increased further and this laid the foundation for institutionally based cooperation formats in the following years. Thus, historical experience and elements of common identity – language, religion, culture and statehood heritage – constitute the ideological and cultural foundations of the modern integration processes of the Turkic-speaking states. This history is not only a memory of the past but also a solid foundation for future cooperation

African and Asian Muslim Organizations

Muslim countries have also launched various integration initiatives in Africa and Asia: The African Islamic Cooperation Organization: was established to protect and develop the rights of Muslim communities. Cooperation initiatives among ASEAN Islamic countries: countries such as Indonesia and Malaysia are trying to establish closer ties with Muslim minorities and countries in their regions. The aim of these initiatives is to preserve Islamic culture as well as expand economic and political cooperation. Organizations such as the OIC, the Coptic Orthodox Church, the Islamic Conference and the Islamic World Council support and promote integration processes in the Muslim world from various perspectives [7]. However there are a number of challenges that limit the impact of the organizations - in particular, the divergent interests of member states, sectarian conflicts and foreign interference. Despite these challenges, institutional cooperation remains an important tool for strengthening the unity of Muslim countries, both regionally and globally.

Obstacles and Challenges:

Political Fragmentation, Sectarian Differences, Foreign Intervention

Integration processes in the Muslim world are constrained by many different factors and these factors stem from both internal and external challenges. Political fragmentation, sectarian differences and foreign intervention are among the main obstacles hindering integration efforts among Islamic countries. These obstacles create great difficulties in promoting unity both regionally and globally.

Political fragmentation and state interests

One of the biggest obstacles to integration in the Muslim world is political fragmentation. Although Islamic countries share a common religious and cultural identity. They have serious differences in their national interests and internal political situations. This political fragmentation has been further deepened by the policies of many Islamic countries after gaining independence, aimed at protecting their sovereignty. Different states in the Islamic world enter into political blocs at various regional and global levels. For example, major states such as Saudi Arabia and Turkey sometimes oppose each other's interests with their claims to regional leadership [9, p. 234]. In addition both religious and political competition between Iran and Saudi Arabia hinders integration processes. The Arab Spring and the instability it brought have further deepened this political fragmentation. As a result many Muslim states are preoccupied with their own internal problems and pay little attention to regional cooperation and integration efforts.

Sectarian differences and religious conflicts

Sectarian differences in the Muslim world are also a significant obstacle to integration processes. The Islamic world is mainly divided into Sunni and Shiite populations. This difference sometimes leads to religious, political and military conflicts. Tensions between the Shiite dominance of Iran and the Sunni leadership of Saudi Arabia shape the foreign policy of many states in the region and in parallel, weaken integration processes. Shiite and Sunni differences are not limited to religious ideologies but also affect civil wars in countries such as Iraq, Syria, Yemen and Bahrain. In addition, the geopolitical rivalry between Saudi Arabia and Iran leads to the deepening of these sectarian conflicts. Thus, sectarian

differences pose a serious obstacle to the establishment of unity in the Islamic world both domestically and regionally.

Foreign Interventions and Global Influences

Foreign interventions are the main factor hindering integration processes in the Islamic world. In recent years the policies of Western states and major powers in the Islamic world and their interference in the internal affairs of these countries play an important role in preventing integration. The regional policies of the US, Russia and China weaken unity among Islamic countries and determine the foreign policy lines of different states.

Events such as the Arab Spring clearly show how foreign interventions affect regional stability and how integration has become difficult. The intervention of the US and NATO especially the conflicts in Libya and Syria have undermined the states trying to create new political and economic systems in the region [13, p.123]. At the same time Iran's nuclear program and the policies implemented by the West and Israel to prevent this program also disrupt regional cooperation and stability processes.

Economic and infrastructure problems

Another important factor that complicates integration in the Muslim world is economic dependence and infrastructure problems. Many Islamic countries are dependent on various foreign powers and international financial institutions which shapes their economic policies. In addition poorly developed infrastructure, customs and trade barriers create serious obstacles to the integration of regional markets. The development of the economy at different levels often slows down regional cooperation. Infrastructure has been damaged as a result of instability and wars in the Middle East and North Africa, which has hindered the development of economic relations. Serious infrastructure projects are needed to increase economic cooperation in the region.

Political fragmentation, sectarian differences and foreign interference are the biggest obstacles preventing integration processes in the Islamic world. Each obstacle in itself stems from both internal and external factors, long-term and strategic approaches are required to overcome these challenges and ensure the formation of deeper cooperation and unity.

Future prospects: proposals for the development of integration

Although integration processes in the Muslim world have a long history, they have not developed to the desired level due to various internal and external challenges. However there are a number of strategies and proposals to make integration efforts more successful and to further advance these processes in the future. These proposals are based on the principles of cooperation and effective governance of both states and international organizations.

Promoting political consensus and cooperation

In order to prevent political fragmentation and promote integration among Islamic countries, political consensus must first be established. This requires more regular and intensive dialogue and cooperation especially among leaders in the region. The OIC and other international organizations should promote broader cooperation at the political level. Joint cooperation on regional and global security issues can also overcome sectarian and ideological differences [5]. To this end special political platforms should be created to strengthen relations between organizations, mutual understanding and solidarity. Further strengthening the role of the OIC is very important to ensure that decisions are taken in the common interests of member states.

Reducing sectarian and religious differences

Reducing sectarian differences is essential to promote integration in the Muslim world. To this end discussions should be organized between both states and religious leaders aimed at overcoming sectarian and ideological differences. Developed educational programs and religious awareness projects can help increase understanding and respect between different sects. Seeing religious diversity as a strength and integrating these differences in a constructive way will help create an environment of social peace and

mutual understanding in Islamic countries. In addition promoting the principles of religious pluralism and tolerance will strengthen the unity of Islamic countries at the national and regional levels.

Strengthening Economic Cooperation

Economic cooperation is one of the main factors for further development of integration in the Muslim world. Expanding trade relations creating common markets and promoting investment flows constitute the basis of economic integration. To this end the resources of the Islamic Development Bank and other financial institutions should be used more purposefully and extensive financial support should be provided for infrastructure projects in Islamic countries. Muslim countries should reduce trade barriers and cooperate on joint economic projects. In addition, regional cooperation in areas such as the energy sector, technology exchange and tourism will allow further development of the economy and strengthen the foundation of integration.

Strengthening security cooperation

Regional security issues are an important part of integration processes. Terrorism, conflicts and security problems exist in many countries in the Muslim world. Joint security platforms and coordination centers should be established to address these problems. The OIC and other international organizations should strengthen security cooperation among member states. Taking joint measures against conflicts in the region will play an important role in ensuring peace and stability. For this purpose, civil and military cooperation and coordination should be more intensive. Considering the balance of power in the region, the states in the region should come together to protect their own interests and represent common interests.

Increasing Humanitarian and Cultural Cooperation

More work should be done in the humanitarian and cultural fields for stronger cooperation among Islamic countries. Educational exchanges, intercultural dialogue and humanitarian aid are important areas of this cooperation. The rich cultural heritage of the Islamic world has great potential to promote unity and mutual understanding [6]. Expanding educational programs among Muslim countries will promote mutual understanding among younger generations and strengthen cultural ties. Also, humanitarian aid initiatives especially aid sent to war and disaster zones will help increase the sense of solidarity in the region. Regional integration processes in the Muslim world are developing at different intensities and forms. Although geographical, political and historical differences hinder the implementation of this process in a unified and sustainable manner, it can be concluded that there are certain efforts in each region and that if these efforts are coordinated, a larger-scale Islamic integration is possible. Long-term and purposeful approaches are required for the development of integration processes in the Muslim world. Political and economic cooperation, overcoming sectarian differences and combating external interference can help establish peace and stability in the region. For the successful implementation of these processes, it is important for all Islamic countries to reach a consensus on common interests. Integration in the Muslim world is of great importance both in terms of internal development and international relations. Every step taken for this purpose will only serve to ensure regional and global stability. The integration process in the Muslim world has tried to move forward against many difficulties and obstacles throughout history. Although Islamic countries have a common structure that unites their common religious and cultural identities, challenges such as political fragmentation, sectarian differences, external interference and economic problems have created serious obstacles to the integration process [14, p.145]. These obstacles are the main factors that make it difficult to ensure unity at both the regional and international levels. However steps such as strengthening existing political and economic structures reducing sectarian differences increasing economic cooperation and developing common approaches to security issues through the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and other international organizations are important for the advancement of integration processes. Measures to be taken especially in the field of education and cultural exchange of the younger generation, may lead to the formation of closer cooperation and mutual understanding in the future. The success of

integration processes depends not only on the joint efforts of states, but also on the people, scientific and cultural organizations. In this world with different religions and cultures, establishing cooperation based on common interests and mutual respect will serve to ensure regional stability and strong unity of Islamic countries.

Iran's Place in the Integration Processes Underway in the Muslim World

Iran is an important actor in the Muslim world in terms of both its historical heritage and its current geopolitical role. Its place and influence in the integration processes have both unifying and divisive aspects [11, p.87].

Iran's Ideological Vision and the Muslim World After the Islamic Revolution of Iran (1979), it began to present itself not only as a nation-state, but also as a power claiming to lead the entire Islamic world. The main features of this ideological approach: promoting a political version of Islam (the model of the Islamic Republic), acting as a "protector of the oppressed" [12 p.321], increasing its regional influence, especially by supporting Shiite communities. Although this ideological line brings Iran closer to some Muslim countries, it also causes serious contradictions with others.

Development and Cooperation Platforms Developed by Iran Iran participates in various cooperation initiatives in the Muslim world: It is a member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and defends its position on its platform. It seeks to cooperate with Turkic and Central Asian countries through economic cooperation organizations (for example, ECO - Economic Cooperation Organization). It establishes cultural and religious ties with Shiite states and countries with Shiite minorities. However, these initiatives of Iran are often perceived as sectarian politics which limits its attempts at broader integration in the Muslim world.

Iran's integration efforts in the Muslim world face serious opponents:

Saudi Arabia: As one of the main leaders of the Sunni world, it stands against Iranian influence. States such as the UAE, Egypt and Bahrain oppose Iran's attempts at regional hegemony. The Gulf countries see Iran's policy in the Middle East (Syria, Yemen, Lebanon) as a threat. These conflicts prevent the deepening of joint integration projects in the Muslim world. Nevertheless, Iran can play a positive role in the Muslim world in certain areas: Iran's successes in science and technology (nuclear energy, medical technologies) create opportunities for cooperation for Muslim countries.

Its promotion of anti-imperialist discourse in the Islamic world is welcomed in some countries. It strengthens relations through cultural and religious diplomacy (especially with Shiite communities).

Iran's Integration Perspectives For Iran to integrate the Muslim world more actively, it is important to: Focus on common Islamic values rather than sectarian politics, Establish diplomatic dialogue with regional rivals.

Pay more attention to economic and scientific cooperation. If Iran can adopt a more pragmatic approach to its policy, it can increase its unifying role in the Muslim world [13, p.134]. Iran is currently an actor that both presents unifying ideas and causes divisions in the Muslim world.

Its role for real integration will be determined by its focus on mutual interests and cooperation rather than ideological expansion. Iran's strengths: Ideological leadership claim, scientific and technological potential, rich history and culture.

Main weaknesses: Highlighting sectarian differences, pursuing a policy that creates instability in the region. Conditions for integration: Developing dialogue with regional rivals, cooperation beyond sectarian differences, strengthening partnerships in the economic and scientific fields. Long-term perspective: Iran can contribute to real integration processes only if it pursues a pragmatic and inclusive policy

Turkey's Role in Integration Processes in the Muslim World

Geopolitical Leadership and Regional Security. Turkey from a geopolitical perspective serves as a bridge between Europe and Asia. Using this position, it is strengthening its relations with both the European Union and Islamic countries. Turkey plays a major role in regional security issues (in Syria,

Iraq, Libya). At the same time as a member of NATO, it establishes close cooperation with the West and has a positive image.

İqtisadi və Ticarət Əməkdaşlığı, Türkiyə, iqtisadi əməkdaşlıq sahəsində də

Economic and Trade Cooperation, Turkey also actively cooperates with Muslim countries in the field of economic cooperation. It is particularly active in the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC).

Turkey's economic potential: Exports, energy cooperation and infrastructure projects. Turkey's position: Strengthening economic development increasing ties through trade and investment.

Sectarian and Cultural Relations

Turkey, in addition to being one of the important leaders of the Sunni Islamic world, also establishes relations with other Muslim countries with its position on multiculturalism and security policy. Sunni-Shia tension: Turkey wants to unite all Muslim countries under the same umbrella in order to eliminate this issue and reduce sectarian approaches. Intercultural relations: It has a unifying role in both cultural and religious matters in the Turkic world. Turkey's Political Role

Turkey is a country with both religious and political influence in the Islamic world. Especially during the Erdogan era, the country has made leadership claims in order to strengthen relations with Muslim countries. Political Alliances: Turkey has increased its political influence by supporting Islamist movements to a certain extent during the Arab Spring events. Political aspect of Islam: Turkey has a wide sphere of influence in its discussions with religious states. International Diplomacy and Multilateral Participation. Turkey actively participates in international organizations such as both the OIC and the UN. This further strengthens its leadership claims in the Muslim world.

Political

Partnerships: Turkey provides development assistance, political dialogues and multilateral discussions in many Muslim countries. Turkey's Integration Perspectives. For Turkey, the issue of integration in the Islamic world seems more real and close in diplomatic, economic and cultural fields. The main conditions necessary for this: Strengthening regional dialogue platforms. Deepening relations with the Turkic world. Developing a model of economic and cultural cooperation around Turkey. Geopolitical position: Turkey plays the role of a bridge between Europe and Asia. Economic power: Turkey strengthens economic cooperation in the Muslim world through modern infrastructure and trade. Cultural leadership: It is an important leader in the Sunni Islamic world. Political influence: Under Erdogan, Turkey has gained more political influence, especially in the Arab world.

Future potential: Turkey's policies for integration are more based on cultural and economic cooperation, Turkey is both an initiator and a participant in integration processes in the Muslim world. Its role in this integration field stems from both geopolitical aspects and economic and cultural relations. Turkey tries to have a positive impact on regional cooperation and unity in the Islamic world, but it also faces regional competition and sectarian differences in order to achieve this goal.

The Role of Arab States in Integration Processes in the Muslim World

Economic Cooperation and Regional Integration. Arab states pay great attention to strengthening economic relations in the Islamic world with countries such as the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Egypt and Qatar. They cooperate together in trade, energy and infrastructure projects. Arab Economic Union: This organization lays the foundation for economic integration among Arab countries but it is difficult to implement it in practice. Cooperation within the framework of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) unites Arab states in the fields of economic development and humanitarian aid. Arab States and Geopolitical Power Arab states, Saudi Arabia and the UAE exert geopolitical influence in the Muslim world through states such as the Arab states. They play an important role in issues such as the Palestinian issue, the Yemeni war and the Iran-Saudi conflict. Saudi Arabia: As the largest economic power in the region, it is the country that makes the main policy and diplomatic decisions in the Arab world. It is known that it leads both the OIC and the Palestinian issue. UAE and Qatar: They are very

active in regional politics and are trying to increase their economic and diplomatic influence in the Middle East.

Sectarian Differences and Regional Tensions. The Sunni-Shia conflict among Arab states complicates some integration efforts. Countries such as Saudi Arabia and the UAE pursue a confrontational policy against Shiite Iran, which hinders security and political cooperation [18, p.345]. **Iran-Saudi conflict:** This conflict weakens integration efforts among Arab states, as each seeks to defend its own interests and regional hegemony. **Bahrain and Lebanon issues:** Hezbollah (a Shiite group supported by Iran) in Lebanon and the Shiite opposition in Bahrain create constant tension among Arab states. **Political Integration in the Islamic World.** Arab states have attempted political integration through the Arab League and other regional organizations. However, political unity is difficult to achieve because the states' different political systems, security interests, and regional instability prevent this. **Arab League:** This organization includes 22 member countries and aims to adopt a common position on political issues, but instability and sectarian differences in the region make unification difficult.

Egypt and Saudi Arabia: They are important players in the struggle for regional leadership, but sometimes they are in conflict with each other in terms of political influence.

Cultural and Religious Role. Arab states have a great cultural and religious influence in the Islamic world, both as religious centers (Mecca, Medina) and as historical centers of Islam [19, p.143]. **Mecca and Medina:** These cities, which are the most important religious centers for Hajj pilgrims, strengthen the religious leadership position of Arab states.

Religious diplomacy: Arab countries take diplomatic steps aimed at protecting religious unity and common values in the Islamic world. **Integration Perspectives of Arab States.** Stronger integration is possible with the reduction of sectarianism and the increase in cooperation based on common interests. Ensuring regional security, strengthening security structures, and greater unity in the areas of economic cooperation can accelerate integration.

Economic relations: Arab states are at the forefront of economic integration initiatives, especially with Saudi Arabia and the UAE. **Geopolitical power:** Arab states, led by Saudi Arabia, have a dominant role in regional security issues. **Sectarian and religious issues:** Sunni-Shia conflict poses an obstacle to integration. **Political unity:** Although there have been attempts at unification through the Arab League and other regional organizations, there are difficulties related to different political systems and security interests. **Cultural and religious influence:** Arab countries have great influence in the Muslim world as the cultural and religious leaders of Islam. Arab states play an important role in the Islamic world in both economic, political and religious spheres. However, their influence in integration processes is often limited due to sectarian politics, regional instability and security issues. If these obstacles are removed, more effective integration is possible through platforms such as the Arab League and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation.

Azerbaijan's Role in Integration Processes in the Muslim World. Immediately after regaining its independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan became a member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) in 1992. During this period, Azerbaijan has gained an influential position within the organization by actively participating in the political, economic, humanitarian and cultural platforms of the OIC. Azerbaijan is located in the strategic center of the South Caucasus and plays the role of a bridge between the East and the West. This position increases its geopolitical influence and creates broad opportunities for cooperation with both the Islamic world and Western states. **Participation in regional conflicts:** The Nagorno-Karabakh conflict has further strengthened Azerbaijan's leadership position in the region. Azerbaijan is also active in regional security issues. **Relations with Iran:** Azerbaijan has long-standing historical relations with Iran, but the strategic partnership with Turkey also occupies an important place in Azerbaijan's geopolitical policy. Azerbaijan actively participates in various economic organizations and platforms in order to strengthen economic relations with the Islamic world. These cooperations are mainly in the oil and gas sector, energy corridors, as well as in the infrastructure sector.

Cooperation within the OIC and ECO: Azerbaijan is active in the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and the Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) and strengthens economic development through these organizations. Azerbaijan has played a leading role in the OIC's activities in various directions. In particular, on the Karabakh issue, the OIC has consistently supported the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Azerbaijan. Within the organization, Armenia's aggressive policy has been condemned, and legal and political support has been expressed for Azerbaijan's rightful position. Azerbaijan has also taken important initiatives in the humanitarian and cultural fields within the OIC. In 2017, Baku was elected the Youth Capital of the OIC, and the IV Islamic Solidarity Games were successfully organized. At the same time, Azerbaijan has made a significant contribution to the development of intercultural dialogue by putting forward initiatives to strengthen Islamic solidarity [1, p.115]. In the economic sphere, Azerbaijan has cooperated with the OIC countries in the implementation of a number of major projects in the fields of transport and energy. Strategic projects such as the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway and the Southern Gas Corridor have turned Azerbaijan into an important transport and energy hub in the OIC space. Projects such as Azerbaijan's Southern Gas Corridor, the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil pipeline, and the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum gas pipeline strengthen economic ties with the Islamic world. Azerbaijan is influential in both the Shia and Sunni worlds. The country cooperates to resolve religious tensions by seeking a balance between representatives of different sects. Religious diversity and tolerance: Azerbaijan, developing its model of multiculturalism, sets the main goal of establishing peace and dialogue between Shia and Sunni Muslims [5]. Protection of holy sites: Azerbaijan also sends pilgrims to the holy cities of Mecca and Medina, strengthening its position through religious diplomacy. Azerbaijan's political influence in the Islamic world stems mainly from its leadership in the South Caucasus and its relations with Turkey. Close relations with Turkey: Azerbaijan has comprehensive strategic cooperation with Turkey, and its activity in the Organization of Turkic States also makes Azerbaijan an important player in the Turkic world. Relations with Iran: Although Azerbaijan has good relations with Iran, it pursues a policy of balance by establishing close relations with Turkey and Western countries. Organization of Islamic Cooperation: Azerbaijan's active participation within the OIC makes it an important player in unifying the Islamic world. Azerbaijan regularly participates in various international organizations to expand its diplomatic relations with the Islamic world. UN, OIC, ECO: Azerbaijan's participation in these organizations increases its diplomatic steps towards solving problems together with the Islamic world. Energy diplomacy: Azerbaijan strengthens its place on international platforms with its energy resources and geopolitical position.

Azerbaijan's Integration Prospects.

The success achieved after the Karabakh war allows Azerbaijan to play a more active role in regional security and stability issues within the OIC. In the future Azerbaijan can come up with new initiatives within the OIC on conflict resolution and promotion of fair approaches based on international law. An initiative to share experience in the field of restoration and reintegration of liberated territories can be implemented through special platforms. Azerbaijan's prospects in integration processes in the Islamic world can develop more through economic, cultural and religious ties. Strategic relations with Turkey: Azerbaijan can strengthen both cultural and economic integration by increasing its activity in the Organization of Turkic States. Closer cooperation with Iran: Azerbaijan can try to create a strong balance between East and West by further developing diplomatic and economic relations with Iran. Azerbaijan as an active participant in the integration processes in the Islamic world strengthens its position through economic, political, religious and cultural ties. Its geopolitical position and strategic cooperation make it one of the key players in the South Caucasus and the Islamic world. Azerbaijan can contribute to the expansion of trade relations between the Islamic world and the "Middle Corridor" project within the OIC. Using the capabilities of the Baku International Sea Trade Port, it will be possible to establish new logistics and trade networks for the OIC countries. At the same time, digital trade, electronic customs systems and investment initiatives based on the principles of Islamic finance can be

among Azerbaijan's priority directions. In the field of science and technology, Azerbaijan can come up with new initiatives to organize joint educational programs within the OIC, hold events such as the Islamic World Science and Technology Forum, and create startup ecosystems. Cooperation opportunities with the OIC member countries can be expanded in the fields of artificial intelligence, green technologies and the digital economy. The creation of an international coalition against Islamophobia in the Islamic world on the initiative of Azerbaijan can be one of the important initiatives. Baku city can become a center for intercultural dialogue and religious tolerance within the OIC in the future. At the same time Azerbaijan's multiculturalism model can be promoted among the OIC countries. Azerbaijan does not limit its position within the Organization of Islamic Cooperation only to existing opportunities, but also defines strategic directions for future development. The success achieved in Karabakh, the growing influence on international platforms and economic potential open up wide opportunities for Azerbaijan to become a more proactive and formative actor in the OIC. Thus, Azerbaijan's role in the OIC will further strengthen in the coming period both regionally and internationally.

Central Asia occupies an important place in Islamic history

This region is the homeland of scholars such as Abu Hanifa, Al-Bukhari, Al-Farabi, Al-Biruni; it has made great contributions to the development of Islamic science. It was also one of the main centers of Islamic culture during the Seljuk and Safavid periods. These countries, while preserving their Islamic heritage, develop cultural ties with the modern Muslim world. In particular, the cities of Samarkand and Bukhara in Uzbekistan play an important role in promoting Islamic heritage through tourism and cultural diplomacy. Activity within the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan are members of the OIC (Organization of Islamic Cooperation) and participate in the political, economic and humanitarian initiatives of this organization. Kazakhstan hosted the OIC Science and Technology Summits (2017, Astana) supporting cooperation between Muslim countries in the field of science. Uzbekistan has sought to strengthen regional cooperation by hosting the next OIC meeting in 2021. Kyrgyzstan promotes the exchange of views with Muslim countries on issues of cultural and religious tolerance. The energy resources and geographical location of these countries make them strategic partners: Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan have rich oil and gas reserves which makes them interested parties in economic integration with the countries of the Middle East. Turkmenistan is expanding access to the energy markets of the Muslim world through Iran and Turkey. These countries are potential partners in projects such as the “Trans-Caspian Energy Corridor”, “TAP” and “TANAP” [3]. Relations with Turkey and Turkish-Islamic integration, Central Asian countries through the Organization of Turkic States (OTS): Cooperate in the fields of culture, language, education and security. This cooperation serves the formation of the Turkish-Islamic unity in parallel with the integration of the Islamic world. Through Turkey, relations with other regions of the Islamic world (especially the Middle East and North Africa) are expanding further. Joint action against terrorism, combating radicalism and promoting the peaceful nature of Islam are among the main priorities of these countries. They: Cooperate in the field of religious enlightenment, and strive to maintain stability in the region by emphasizing the role of Islam in the secular state model. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan and Kyrgyzstan play an active role in the integration processes taking place in the Muslim world, in areas such as activity within the framework of organizations (OIC, TDT), combating radicalism and religious enlightenment. Their contribution to these processes is important both in terms of strengthening regional stability and general Islamic solidarity.

Conclusion.

Throughout history, a number of conflicts between Muslim countries (Iraq-Iran war, Kuwait crisis, etc.) have damaged mutual trust.

Even today the parties do not show complete trust in each other, and this prevents the deepening of integration. These factors show that for real integration in the Muslim world, only common religious and cultural values are not enough. At the same time, political will, mutual trust, interfaith dialogue and

common strategic interests must be formed. Integration processes in the Muslim world are a multifaceted issue that is of great importance both in the historical and contemporary context. The success of these processes depends on many factors - political will, economic opportunities, cultural and religious common values, as well as the reconciliation of geopolitical interests. At the current stage, although regional associations such as the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) are promoting certain aspects of integration, the overall picture reflects a fragmented and unevenly developing process. Despite common religious and cultural ties among Muslim countries, the primacy of national interests, differences in political systems, and in some cases mutual distrust hinder the deepening of integration. In addition, the under-fulfillment of the potential in the field of economic cooperation, limited trade relations and technological dependence also lead to the weakening of this process. Consequently, political stability, mutual trust, economic diversification, and a common strategic vision are required, first of all, to strengthen integration in the Muslim world. At the same time, the development of cultural diplomacy and scientific and technological cooperation can also play an important role in the formation of common platforms. If coordination in these areas is strengthened, the Muslim world can act as a more effective and united actor in the global arena. Integration in the Muslim world is of great importance not only in terms of regional integration, but also in terms of ensuring stability at the global level. The successful implementation of this process will allow not only to solve existing problems, but also to establish stronger and more sustainable cooperation between these countries in the future. The idea of Islamic integration is based on both religious and political foundations. Although organizations such as the OIC and the GCC have taken important steps in modern times, real integration has not yet been fully realized. Sectarianism, geopolitical competition and economic inequality are among the main obstacles. In the future, technology, education and joint economic projects can strengthen integration between Muslim countries. Although the desire for integration is based on a common Islamic identity and a common historical heritage, serious problems remain at the level of practical implementation. Joint organizations exist between Muslim countries (OIC, GCC, etc.), but their effectiveness is limited and they operate mainly at the level of political statements. Sectarian differences, diversity in political systems, economic inequality and external influences create serious obstacles to integration efforts.

Future prospects:

Strengthening the regional cooperation model: First, increasing integration initiatives at the regional level (for example, between the Gulf countries, North Africa, and Muslim countries in Asia) seems more realistic. Developing interfaith dialogue: Promoting mutual understanding and religious tolerance in Sunni-Shia relations is a necessary condition for integration. Expanding economic cooperation initiatives: Supporting joint economic projects through the Islamic Development Bank and other institutions. The role of the young generation in integration: Strengthening the awareness of common Islamic solidarity in the new generation through joint programs in the fields of education, science, and technology. As a result, the future of integration in the Muslim world will depend on the existence of mutual political will among states, the prioritization of common interests, and the overcoming of historical crises of confidence.

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